

Integration of machine learning in Ayurveda: An Indian traditional health science

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Abstract

Machine learning is one of the fast-growing areas of computer science, with far-reaching applications. There are several applications for machine learning. The most significant of which is supervised learning. Supervised learning is common in classification problems. In this paper, we presents a comprehensive review of utilizing and integrating machine learning (ML) techniques in Ayurveda - a traditional healthcare system, which roots in ancient Indian philosophy. Ayurveda emphasizes a holistic approach to health and well-being, focusing on individuals' constitution (Prakriti) and Panchamahabhuta, dosha imbalances (Vata, Pitta, and Kapha), lifestyle factors, environmental factors, and personalized treatments. The integration of ML algorithms in Ayurveda opens up new possibilities for enhancing diagnosis, treatment recommendation, patient management, and research in this ancient system.

The paper begins by discussing the fundamental principles of Ayurveda, different methods and modules in ML for various roles in Ayurveda. It thus delves into various areas where ML can be beneficial, including pattern recognition in Ayurvedic texts (Samhita), personalized treatments based on Prakriti and health conditions, disease prediction and prevention by analysing dosha imbalances and lifestyle factors, and Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) for Ayurvedic practitioners. Also, this paper explores how ML can contribute to Quality Control (QC) and authentication of Ayurvedic medicines, patient health monitoring through wearable devices and IoT sensors, public health surveillance by analysing population-level data, and the integration of Ayurvedic knowledge with modern healthcare practices. Overall, this paper aims to provide insights into the promising synergies between traditional Ayurvedic wisdom and modern ML technologies, paving the way for innovative and personalized healthcare solutions grounded in ancient wisdom and scientific rigor.

Keywords: Ayurveda, Machine Learning, Dosha, Prakriti, Samhita etc.

1. Introduction

Ayurveda [1] is an Indian Traditional Health science which has been originated in India over 5000 years ago. Wisdom of this science is rooted in the manuscripts called *Samhita* - such as *Charak Samhita*, *Sushrut Samhita*, *Vagbhat Samhita*. In Ayurveda, treatment is based on holistic approach to health and well - being, mainly focusing on doshas (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) and individual's constitution (Prakruti) and harmony between mind, body and spirit. The fundamental principle of ayurveda emphasises preventive healthcare, personalised treatments, natural remedies, lifestyle modifications, and eating habits (Dincharya, Aharcharya and Rutucharya) to promote health and longevity. The important objective of Ayurvedic diagnosis is, it aims to identify the underlying imbalance and root-causes of health issue, rather than just treating symptoms, which helps to attend long-lasting treatment effect, improvement in health and well-being.

Now talking about Machine Learning [2], machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that focuses on developing algorithms and statistical models that enable computers to learn and make predictions or decisions based on the data. The ability to learn from experience data, improve overtime and make predictions or decisions without human intervention is the super important feature of machine learning. This is achieved through the process of training a model using label data or unlabelled data. Machine learning algorithms can be categorised into four main types such as supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi supervised learning and reinforcement learning.

The integration of Machine learning in Ayurveda holds immense potential across various domains such as - pattern recognition in ayurvedic texts, personalised treatment and recommendation based on Prakriti and health conditions. Machine learning can be used in disease prediction and prevention, CDSS for practitioners, quality control of Ayurvedic medicine, patient health monitoring and public health surveillance.

2. Utilisation of Machine Learning in Ayurveda

2.1 Pattern Recognition

In Ayurvedic Samhitas: Machine learning algorithms can analyse large volumes of Ayurvedic texts to identify patterns, correlations, and relationships between herbs, diseases, symptoms, and treatments. This can help in understanding traditional Ayurvedic concepts and principles more comprehensively [3].

2.2 Medicine Recommendation Systems:

Machine learning models can be trained on Ayurvedic principles and historical data to recommend personalized herbal medicines or formulations based on an individual's constitution (Prakriti), health conditions, lifestyle, and preferences [4].

2.3 Disease Prediction and Prevention:

By integrating Ayurvedic principles with modern health data, machine learning algorithms can predict the risk of diseases based on factors such as dosha imbalances, lifestyle habits, and environmental factors. This can enable proactive preventive healthcare interventions [5].

2.4 Clinical Decision Support Systems:

Machine learning can assist Ayurvedic practitioners in making evidence-based decisions by analysing patient data, historical treatment outcomes, and Ayurvedic guidelines. This can enhance treatment efficacy and patient outcomes [4].

2.5 Quality Control and Authentication:

Machine learning techniques such as image recognition and spectroscopy can be used to authenticate herbal products, ensure quality control, detect adulteration, and verify the presence of active compounds in Ayurvedic medicines [1].

2.6 Public Health Surveillance:

Machine learning can analyse population-level health data, Ayurvedic clinical trials, and epidemiological studies to identify trends, outbreaks, and patterns of disease prevalence. This information can guide public health policies and interventions [6].

3 Methodology

3.1 Types of Machine Learning Techniques:

Machine learning algorithms [2] are mainly divided into four categories: Supervise learning, Unsupervised learning, Semi supervise learning and Reinforcement learning as shown figure 1 depicts the basic types of ML techniques.

Supervise learning is typically the task of ML to learn from the given input output data for further predictions. It used level data for the learning procedure. Basically, supervise learning teaches a computer to do something by showing it examples. The ML model learns from labelled training data. E.G email spam detection. Algorithm of classification and regression are commonly used in supervise learning.

Unsupervised learning analyses unlabelled datasets without the need for human interference called as data

driven processes. Algorithms of clustering are commonly used in unsupervised learning. Also, the most common unsupervised learning task is density estimation, feature learning, dimensional reduction, association rules, and anomaly detection.

Semi supervised learning can be defined as combination of supervised and unsupervised learning methods, since it operates on labelled and unlabelled data. And finally, Reinforcement learning is a type of ML algorithm that enables software to bring an environment driven approach. This learning is based on reward or penalty, and its ultimate goal is to use insights obtain from environmental activists to take action to increase the reward or minimise the risk.

Thus, to build effective models in the various application areas, different types of ML techniques can play a very significant role, depending on the nature of data and target outcome in the field of health sciences.

Figure1: Various types of Machine Learning

3.2 Classifications of Machine Learning Algorithms Approaches

In this paper, we have studied different classification algorithms. Classification has numerous applications, including fraud de-tection, target marketing, performance prediction, manufacturing, and medical diagnosis. Data classification is a two-step process, consisting of a learning step (where a classification model is constructed) and a classification step (where

the model is used to predict class labels foe given data). Classification techniques assign or classify data records into categories of a class variable. Classification method is good for prediction of the outcome that is represented by categorical variables.

The following are the different classification algorithms: Linear Regression (LR), Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Tree, Random Forest (RF), Support Vector

Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Neural Networks (NN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM).

Linear Regression (LR) Linear regression [2] is a supervised learning algorithm used for predicting a continuous dependent variable based on one or more independent variables. It assumes a linear relationship between the input features and the target variable.

Logistic Regression (LR) Logistic regression is a binary classification algorithm used to predict the probability of an event occurring (e.g., yes/no, disease/no disease). It models the relationship between the input features and the probability of the target variable belonging to a specific class.

Decision Tree (DT) are versatile supervised learning algorithms that can be used for both classification and regression tasks. They split the data into branches based on feature thresholds, creating a tree-like structure for decision-making.

Random Forest (RF) is an ensemble learning technique that combines multiple decision trees to improve predictive accuracy and reduce overfitting. It randomly selects subsets of features and data points for each tree and aggregates the predictions.

Support Vector Machines (SVM) is a powerful supervised learning algorithm used for classification tasks. It finds the optimal hyperplane that separates different classes in the feature space by maximizing the margin between the classes.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a simple and intuitive algorithm used for both classification and regression tasks. It makes predictions based on the majority class (for classification) or average value (for regression) of the K nearest neighbours in the training data.

Naive Bayes (NB) is a probabilistic classification algorithm based on Bayes' theorem with the "naive"

assumption of independence between features. It calculates the probability of a data point belonging to a particular class given its features.

Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) is an ensemble learning technique that builds a series of weak learners (typically decision trees) sequentially. Each new model corrects errors made by the previous ones, gradually improving predictive accuracy.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is an unsupervised learning technique used for dimensionality reduction. It transforms high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional space while retaining as much variance as possible, thereby capturing the most important features.

Neural Networks (NN)

Neural networks are a class of deep learning models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. They consist of interconnected layers of neurons that learn complex patterns and relationships in data.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) is a type of neural network designed for sequence data, where the output at each time step depends not only on the current input but also on previous inputs (memory). They are commonly used in natural language processing and time series analysis.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is a variant of RNNs designed to address the vanishing gradient problem and capture long-term dependencies in sequential data. It includes memory cells and gating mechanisms to control the flow of information.

4 Related works

There are various researches has been done in the field of Ayurveda and machine learning applications in Ayurveda. An international journal of research in Ayush and allied systems named Ayushdhara publishes various research works and review works in the field of Ayurveda and the integration of artificial intelligence in Ayurveda [1]. Vishu Madaan and Anjali Goyal has worked on prediction of Ayurveda based constitute

balancing in human body using machine learning methods [8]. Roopashree et al. have worked on the study of Ayurvedic herbs using machine learning techniques in their research [9]. Vani Rajasekar et al. worked on the prediction of Ayurveda based constituent in the human body using different machine learning methods. In their research work, the assemble machine learning methods to predict the balancing of Ayurvedic constituents in the human body [10].

Chairote Yaiprasert et al. have worked on AI for target symptoms of Thai herbal medicine by wave scrapping model in machine learning [3]. Shrinivas Jhade et al. worked on a clinical decision support system through the utilisation of machine learning models in their research work [5]. Anum Masood et al. have also worked on the clinical decision support system using machine learning modules [4]. Christos Stefansis et al. worked on the analysis of epidemiological surveillance report on COVID-19 using ML modules [6].

5 Adoption and Implementation Challenges

Integrating machine learning with traditional healthcare systems like Ayurveda requires careful consideration of cultural, ethical, and regulatory aspects. Collaboration between Ayurvedic experts, data scientists, healthcare professionals, and regulatory authorities is essential to ensure responsible and effective use of modern technology in Ayurvedic healthcare.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we have a comprehensive review of utilizing and integrating machine learning (ML) techniques in Ayurveda - a traditional healthcare system. We try to present the usage of modern technology, such as machine learning in the field of Ayurveda. It aims to explore the synergy between ancient Ayurvedic wisdom and modern machine, learning technologies, highlighting the opportunities, challenges, methodologies, and future direction. In this rapidly involving in the field of health science. Through

interdisciplinary collaboration and ethical considerations, the integration of machine learning in Ayurveda has the potential to revolutionise healthcare delivery, enhance patient outcomes and contribute to global advancement of personalised medicine.

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